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Evaluation of new reduction technique for acute anterior shoulder dislocation.

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Abstract

Background: Traumatic shoulder dislocation is relatively common serious injury in sports activities, because of its inherent anatomy and biomechanics, shoulder joint is one of the most unstable and frequently dislocated joints in body, accounting for nearly 50% of all dislocations. Therefore dislocated shoulder should reduced as quickly and as gentle as possible to prevent further soft tissue damage and to maintain its normal stability by simple, harmless method of reduction. The aim of this study was to evaluate efficacy of new simple and gentle method of reduction technique for anterior shoulder dislocation.

Patients and Methods: Seventeen Patients (15 men, 2 women), their age ranging from (18 – 55) years old with traumatic anterior shoulder dislocation whom were treated by a new abduction horizontal-adduction technique, in outpatient clinic and emergency department in Al Karkh general hospital in Baghdad, over 6 months period during the year 2001. From these 17 patients, 13 patients have primary dislocations, 3 have recurrent dislocations and one patient have old neglected dislocation.

Results: 16 patients (94%) have successful reduction from the first trial by using this abduction - horizontal adduction technique, without using any anesthesia or assistance. Only one patient had reduction under general anesthesia because his dislocations associated with fracture of both greater and the lesser tuberosity, in addition to muscular body and complained from severe pain and anxiety. The follow up period of those patients for about one and half year showed no immediate complications such as (neurovascular injuries, additional fractures, nor recurrent dislocation, was reported after reduction.

Keywords: Shoulder- Dislocation reduction–New technique.

Introduction

Traumatic shoulder dislocation is relatively common serious injury in sports activities [1], because of its inherent anatomy and biomechanics, shoulder joint is one of the most unstable and frequently dislocated joints in body, accounting for nearly 50% of all

dislocations [2]. Therefore dislocated shoulder should be reduced as quickly and as gentle as possible to prevent further soft tissue damage and to maintain its normal stability by simple, harmless method of reduction. Shoulder (glenohumeral) joint has small bony articulation, and glenoid fossa is a flattened dishlike structure, with only one fourth of the large humeral head articulate with glenoid at any given position[3] The small, flat glenoid bony area, does not provide inherent stability for humeral head as the acetabulum does for the hip. But the glenoid deepened further more about 50% by presence of glenoid labrum which increase the humeral head contact to about 75%. The shoulder joint can perform greater freedom of movement with a considerable loss of stabilization.

Patients and Methods

Seventeen Patients (15 men, 2 women), their age ranging from (18 – 55) years old with traumatic anterior shoulder dislocation whom were treated by abduction – horizontal adduction technique, in outpatient clinic and emergency department in Al Karkh general hospital in Baghdad, over 6 months period during the year 2001. From these 17 patients, 13 patients have primary dislocations, 3 have recurrent dislocations and one patient have old neglected dislocation. Dislocation was diagnosed clinically and radiologically before reduction. Each patient was placed in supine position on examining table to start reduction by reassurance of patient and to make him relaxed as much as possible without

any medication. With the physician standing on the side of the dislocation, holding the wrist of dislocated shoulder by one hand to start gently and slowly abduction of extended upper extremity, till reach 90° of abduction, avoiding as possible patient discomfort during abduction, the patients felt some what anxious about this maneuver, but they didn't experience severe pain. Now at 90° abduction, with the same physician's hand gentle axial traction with horizontal adduction applied to extended upper extremity of patient while the thumb of other hand placed against humeral head to check reduction plus applying some pressure to assist reduction till reduction done, which often complete with this step in about 45° of horizontal adduction. , lastly the arm was brought down to the side for checking joint mobility and then immobilized with sling and swathe. Figure (1).

Results: 16 patients (94%) have successful reduction from the first trial by using this abduction – horizontal adduction technique, without using any anesthesia or assistance. Only one patient had reduction under general anesthesia because his dislocation associated with fracture of both greater and the lesser tuberosity, in addition to muscular body and complained from severe pain and anxiety. The follow up period of those patients for about one and half year showed no immediate complications such as (neurovascular injuries, additional fractures, nor recurrent dislocation).

A

B

C

Figure(1) : Shows stages of reduction method: (A)45o gentle abduction of extende arm , (B) then 90o abduction with slight gentle axiall traction, (c) horizotal addaction extended arm while thumb of other hand pressing on the head of humerus to complet reduction.

Discussion

Analysis of reduction mechanism: at 60° abduction of affected upper extremity, scapula was slightly rotated compared with starting position and with continued upward elevation up to 90° abduction, scapula will shift more anteriorly with superior rotation along thoracic wall. With horizontal adduction, scapula reach maximum shifting anteriorly and rotating superiorly leading the humeral head to be externally rotated and then reduce at this point .The anatomy of the shoulder joint reveal three kinds of structures and factors which can play role in shoulder joint stability such as, capsular ligaments and four muscle groups in addition to scapular mobility and other factors [1, 3].From biceps tubercle at superior rim of glenoid and passes distally in the bicipital groove, guides the dislocated humeral head moves in direction of glenoid fossa during final stages of reduction. So the long head of biceps tendon seems to have important role in this reduction technique along with the musculotendinosus units of rotator cuff and scapular shifting and rotation. Milch H reported [4] that the complete overhead abduction is the only position in which a simple force, exerted along the axis of humerus is directed to overcome each and all muscle action at the same time, so the overhead position aligns the shoulder musculature and minimizes muscle spasm, there by increasing comfort and facilitating reduction.

Recently , many authors have described numerous techniques to reduce a dislocated shoulder because the old methods of reduction such as Hippocratic technique or Kocher

leverage technique , although they are still effective but frequently fails in muscular and obese patients and some times produced iatrogenic humeral neck fractures in elderly patients and may injure other soft tissue such as anterior capsule , glenoid labrum and neurovascular structures which may lead to further complications and shoulder instability[5,6,7,8,] By comparing the results of Hiromoto. et al[9] who reported 91% success rate (41 from 45 dislocations) reduced successfully, with our results with 94% success rate (16 from 17 dislocations reduced successfully).This new reduction technique can give good results when used properly. Further more most methods required general anesthesia and assistant , while this method of reduction , maintain or provide simple maneuver without using assistance or analgesia minimizes further soft tissue damage and can be easily done in obese or muscular patients.

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